

SYNTHESIS OF GRAPHENE QUANTUM DOTS FROM LOW COST MATERIALS AND FABRICATION OF NANOCOMPOSITES

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Abstract

Carbon-based nanomaterials have attracted great interest due to their unique mechanical, chemical, electrical, thermal, and biological properties. They have been used in many applications such as photovoltaic devices, bioimaging, drug delivery, and nanocomposites. Among all carbon based materials, graphene has taken a lot of interest by researchers since its discovery. However, graphene does not have a band gap which prevents the optical and electrical applications. Graphene Quantum Dots (GQDs), which are zero dimensional graphene derivatives with a tunable band gap and functionalities on the edges and basal plane, have many applications in solar cells, bioimaging, photoluminescent materials, and nanocomposites. GQDs with many functional groups are promising with their ability of making strong interactions with the polymer matrix through abundant functionalities. Recently, GQDs have been incorporated into the polymer matrix to create luminescent polymer composite films which can be applied to flexible electronic displays, LEDs, and optoelectronics. It has been demonstrated that brightness, tensile strength, toughness, and Young's modulus of polymers can be improved by addition of GQDs into the polymer matrix. In the current study, GQDs were synthesized from a relatively low cost material, citric acid, with a very high luminescent properties in one pot hydrothermal method. Produced GQDs were characterized using UV-vis spectroscopy, FTIR, ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR, XPS, XRD, Raman to reveal the functionalities and graphitic nature of synthesized GQDs. After a comprehensive characterization, bright luminescent polymers with a relatively small amount of GQDs were created by successful incorporation of GQDs into a polymer matrix which open doors to possible applications such as electronic displays, LEDs, and optoelectronic applications.

Background

Figure 1. Structures of graphene-based materials [1]

Figure 2. Properties of Graphene Quantum Dots

Figure 3. Synthesis of GQDs with top-down and bottom-up approaches (reproduced with permission [2])

Synthesis and Applications

Figure 4. Precursors and applications of GQDs

Synthesis and Incorporation into Polymer Matrix

Figure 5. Cell imaging of GQDs and Incorporation of GQDs into silicagel for LED applications (reproduced with permission [3])

Figure 6. GQDs under UV light, UV-vis spectroscopy of GQDs and DSC of composite films

Figure 7. Polymer-GQDs under UV light and UV-vis spectroscopy of polymer, polymer with 1% GQDs and 3% of GQDs, respectively

References

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